

Mapping the Influence: Government Expenditure and Its Role in Boosting HDI in Bengkulu's Cities and Regencies, Indonesia

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Abstract: *The study aims to analyze the impact of health function expenditure, education function expenditure, economic function expenditure, and social protection function expenditure on the human development index in districts/cities in Bengkulu Province. As for the type of data and analytical tools used in this study, panel data and double linear regression analysis. Based on the results of panel data regression, the random effect model was obtained as the best model. As for the results of research based on the trial, the results were obtained that partially education function expenditure has a negative impact on the human development index, while health function expenditure and economic function expenditure have a positive and significant effect on the index of human development, while social protection expenditure has no influence on the Human Development Index in the district/city in Bengkulu Province. Meanwhile, simultaneously education function expenditure, health function expenditure, economic function expenditure and social protection function expenditure have a positive impact on human development Index in districts/cities in the province. The value of the coefficient determined in this research model is 0.6631, which means that the capacity of the variable education function expenditure, health function expenditure, economic function expenditure and social protection function expenditure were able to explain the human development index of 66.31 percent, while 33.69 percent was described by variables outside the model. Furthermore, based on the results of this study, the Government of the district/city of Bengkulu Province could raise the human development index by maximizing the management of expenditure on health functions and expenditure on economic functions, as well as improving the pattern of allocation of funds on education functions so that it could affect the increase in the average school life and school life expectancy of the people of the province of Bengkulu, and provide social protection assistance to the people who are truly economically vulnerable.*

Keywords: *Human Development Index, health function expenditure, education function expenditure, economic function expenditure, social protection functional expenditure.*

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Introduction

Human resources are one of the factors that influence the success of managing the potential resources that a region possesses. In this case, human beings are valuable assets as well as subjects in development. In endogenous economic growth, human resources with the power of science, natural resources, technological assets and institutions, are the most important things in the model. (Romer, 1994). Besides, in theory, development determined by human capital has been much discussed by economists. Adam Smith not only raised about laissez-faire policy, but also paid great attention to development. According to Todaro and Smith (2003), development has three core values: achievement of life sustenance, self-esteem, and freedom or freedom. (Freedom). By pursuing the success of these three core values of

development a country can come out of economic lag. According to Jhinghan (2007), to change the economic backwardness and arouse the ability and motivation to move forward, it is important to improve the knowledge and skills of the people. Without improvement in quality and human factor, there can be no progress in the economy of a country.

In an attempt to analyze the comparative status of socio-economic development in a comprehensive manner in both developing and developed countries, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) has this in its Human Development Report (HDR). As for one of the indicators that can be used to measure the outcome of development is by looking at the level of well-being and quality of life of the people through the value of the Human Development Index. (HDI). Here's a

comparison of the human development index in Bengkulu Province and Indonesia (see figure 1). Based on figure 1, it can be seen that the human development index of the district/city in Bengkulu Province tends to increase from year to year. According to the Central Statistical Authority, on average, the HDI of the districts/cities in Bengkulu Province is in the middle category. However, the human development index of this province is still below the national HDI average. This indicates that the welfare level of the people of Bengkulu Province is still below the well-being of the Indonesian people in general. Especially in the areas of education, health and decent living that are still relatively low compared to other provinces.

Figure 1. Comparison of the Human Development Index of Bengkulu Province and Indonesia

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics, Bengkulu Province (data is processed)

According to the Central Bureau of Statistics, measuring human development uses the composite indicator HDI, which is organized on the health index, the education index, and the dignified standard of living index. In the 2004 Indonesian Human Development Report, which is a joint publication of the Central Bureau of Statistics, National Development Planning Agency and UNDP, it is stated that one of the most important tasks of development is to translate economic growth into enhanced human development. (Evianto, 2010). According to Goddess (2014) the level of human development can affect the ability of the population to manage various resources to drive economic growth. Furthermore, according to Fitri (2012), the cause of poverty in a country is the low quality of human resources consisting of the quality of education and human health.

As for one of the efforts made by the government to raise the human development index, it has issued a number of budgets in the areas of education, health, economics and social protection. During 2017-2021, the district/city government in Bengkulu Province issued expenditure on education, health, economic and social protection functions with amounts that were constantly fluctuating and tended to increase from year to year. As for the average expenditure of education functions and health functions of districts/cities in Bengkulu Province can be seen in figure 2.

If viewed based on the amount of expenditure on education and health functions, during 2017-2021, the Bengkulu Provincial government tends to spend a considerable amount of spending. In this case, expenditure on education functions and expenditure on health functions is one of the forms of non-physical expenditure carried out by the government to increase the productivity of human resources which will ultimately have an impact on the

welfare of the community. As stated in the theory of human capital, it is said that a person can increase his income through education. As found by research by Marlin, et al (2022), Atmanti (2005), that expenditure on educational functions affects the human development index. Likewise with government expenditure in the health sector. Basically, the goal is to increase the productivity of human resources. According to Todaro and Smith (2003), government expenditure on the health sector is a requirement for increasing people's productivity. As a result of research conducted by Barro (1996), health status as measured by life expectancy is the main contributor to economic growth, even its position is more important than education.

Figure 2. Average Expenditure on Education Functions, Health Function Expenditures, Economic Function Expenditures and Social Protection Function Expenditures by Regency/City in Bengkulu Province in 2017-2021

Source: Directorate General of Fiscal Balance Ministry of Finance

According to Razmi et. All (2012), with the improvement of health, it will increase productivity and labor supply. In addition to expenditure on education and health functions, the government also spends on economic functions and social protection function expenditure. According to Sutono (2022), the allocation of government expenditure for the economic sector and social protection carried out to provide guarantees that people have wide job opportunities so that they can have adequate income. Job opportunities and high income levels will also be easily obtained by people with a good level of education and health conditions. Therefore, indirectly government expenditure in the economic and social protection sectors will also affect the improvement of people's welfare (HDI).

If you look at the development of government expenditure (see figure 2), the Bengkulu Provincial government spends government expenditure constantly fluctuating and tends to increase from year to year. The amount of expenditure incurred by the government is not a small number, which is expected to be able to provide benefits to the improvement of human resources in Bengkulu Province. However, on the other hand, if you look at it based on the human development index (see figure 1), the development index of Bengkulu Province is still far below the national average HDI. Therefore, the researcher is interested in conducting a more in-depth study on whether expenditure on health functions, expenditure on education functions, expenditure on economic functions and expenditure on social protection have an impact on the human development index in districts/cities in Bengkulu Province or not.

Methods

This study uses a quantitative descriptive method. The data used is secondary data in the form of panel data obtained from the Central Statistics Agency of Bengkulu Province and the Directorate General of Fiscal Balance (Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia) during 2017-2021. The variables used are the human development index (HDI) as a dependent variable and expenditure on education functions, expenditure on health functions, expenditure on economic functions and expenditure on social protection functions as independent variables. Furthermore, this data will be analyzed using an analysis tool, namely panel data regression. The equation model of this research is:

$$HDI = \alpha + \beta_1 EdE_{it} + \beta_2 HE + \beta_3 EcE_{it} + \beta_4 SosE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where HDI is the Human Development Index, α is a constant, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ is the regression coefficient of education function expenditure and health function expenditure, economic function expenditure and social protection function expenditure, respectively, EdE is education function expenditure, HE is health function expenditure

EcE is economic function expenditure, SosE is social protection function expenditure, i is cross section unit, t is time series (2017-2021), and ε is Error term.

The use of panel data in an observation has several advantages obtained. In the estimation method of the regression model of panel data, it can be done through three approaches, namely the Common Effect, fixed effect and Random Effect approaches (Widarjono, 2009).

Results and Discussions

In the regression of the panel data, to determine the best model between Common Effect, fixed effect and Random Effect was carried out with 3 tests. The three tests are the chow test, the hausman test, and the lagrange multiplier test. In analyzing panel data, the first test carried out was the chow test. The chow test was carried out to choose between the common effect model and the fixed effect model. Based on the results of the chow test, the following results were obtained:

Table 1. Chow Test Results

Effects Test	Stat.	df	Prob.
Cross-section F	235.524155	(9.36)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	228.931576	9	0.0000

Source: Secondary data (processed, 2022)

Based on the chow test, a cross-section probability value of F of 0.0000 was obtained. The value of the cross-section probability of F is smaller than the value of α (0.05), so the best model to use is the fixed effect model. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a hausman test to determine the best model between the fixed effect model and the random effect model. The results of the hausman test can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Hausman Test Results

Test Summary	Chi-sq.Stat.	Chi-sq. d.f	Prob.
Cross-section random	6.632842	4	0.1566

Source: Secondary data (processed, 2022)

Based on Table 2, the probability of random cross-section is obtained at 0.1566. This probability value is greater than the value of α (0.05), so the best model is a random effect model. Because the model was chosen as a random effect model, it is necessary to carry out further testing of the best model between the random effect model and the common effect model. The results of the lagrange multiplier test can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Lagrange Multiplier Test Results

	Cross-section	Test Hypothesis Time	Both
Breush-Pagan	83.00700 (0.0000)	1.144029 (0.2848)	84.15103 (0.0000)

Source: Secondary data (processed, 2022)

Based on Table 3, the Breush-Pagan cross-section is obtained by 0.0000. This probability value is smaller than the value of α (0.05), so the best model is a random effect model. The results of the best random effect model can be seen in the following Tabel.

Table 4. Best Model Results (Random Effect Model)

Variable	Coeff.	Std. Err.	t-Stat.	Prob.
C	68.0842	1.211109	56.21575	0.0000 ***
EdE	-5.26E-12	1.23E-12	-4.265830	0.0001 ***
HE	1.51E-11	2.30E-12	6.575768	0.0000 ***
EcE	4.12E-12	1.67E-12	2.466166	0.0175 **
SosE	-1.60E-11	1.52E-11	-1.049592	0.2995

R²: 0.6906

Adjusted R-Square : 0.6631

F-statistic : 25.11150

Prob (F-Statistic) : 0.000231

Signif.codes : 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Source : Secondary Data (processed, 2023)

Based on the test results in Table 1, the regression equation is obtained as follows;

$$HDI = 68.0842 - 5.26E - 12 * EdE_{it} + 1.51E - 11 * HE_{it} + 4.12E - 12 * EcE_{it} - 0.60E - 11 * SosE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Hypothesis testing is carried out to find out whether the hypothesis that has been established is accepted or rejected statistically. This statistical test was carried out by t-test, F-test, and determination coefficient test (R2). Based on the results of the determination coefficient test, an R-square value of 0.6631 was obtained. This value shows that the ability of the variables health function expenditure, education function expenditure, economic function and social protection expenditure is able to explain the human development index of 66.31 percent, while 33.69 percent is explained by variables outside the model. Furthermore, based on the F test, an F-Statistic value of 25.11150 was obtained with a probability of 0.000000. until Ho is rejected and H1 accepted. These results show that simultaneously the variables of health function expenditure, education function expenditure, economic

function and social protection function expenditure have a positive and significant effect on the human development index in α (0.05).

Then based on the t-test, the t-Statistical value of the education function expenditure variable was obtained of -4.26580 (negative) with a t-Statistical probability of 0.0001. This t-statistic probability number is less than α (0.05), so H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. These results show that education function expenditure has a negative and significant effect on the human development index at α (0.05). Furthermore, the t-Statistical value of the health function expenditure variable is 6.575768 (positive) with a t-Statistical probability of 0.0000. This probability number is smaller α (0.05), so H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. These results show that health function expenditure has a positive and significant effect on the human development index at α (0.05). Meanwhile, the t-Statistics value of the economic function variable is 2.466166 (positive) with a probability value of 0.0175. This t-statistic probability number is less than α (0.05), so H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. These results show that economic function expenditure has a positive and significant effect on the human development index at α (0.05). Furthermore, the t-Statistical value of social protection function expenditure is -1.049592 with a probability value of 0.2995. This t-statistic probability number is less than α (0.05), so H_0 is accepted and H_1 is rejected. These results show that social protection expenditure has no effect on the human development index at α (0.05).

Discussion

Based on the t-test, the results were obtained that partially education function expenditure had a negative and significant effect on the human development index at α (5%). These results show that when there is an increase in education function expenditure, but the human development index decreases and vice versa, when the education function expenditure decreases, the human development index increases. When viewed from research data, education function expenditure in 2017-2021 always fluctuates and decreases, while the human development index always increases from year to year. In addition, if viewed based on the data of the dimensions that form HDI, all dimensions that form HDI have indeed increased, both the dimensions of longevity and healthy living, the dimension of knowledge, and the dimension of decent living standards. However, the increase in the knowledge dimension represented by the School Length Expectancy and the Average School Length, is still relatively lower when compared to the increase in other HDI forming dimensions. This shows that government policies in the field of education have not had a significant impact on increasing the human development index in Regencies/Cities in Bengkulu Province. This is due to the pattern of education function expenditure issued by the government, which is mostly used for employee expenditure, while capital expenditure, goods and services, and other expenditures are still relatively small (Septriani, 2023); Septriani et.al (2020).

Mongan (2019), said that this ineffective education expenditure will only burden the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget and state budget, as a result of mandatory spending that must be provided by the government. However, in this case, the local government can actually allocate education function expenditure for other productive things, so that it has an impact on increasing the average length of school and the expected length of school, as well as other dimensions of knowledge. Anand

and Ravallion (1993), stated that the high level of education and health will have an impact on increasing the productivity of the community, which may have previously been included in the category of poor and poorly educated. According to Lestari (2021), expenditure in the education sector will only be felt in the long term, especially as can be seen from the increase in human resources and increased labor productivity.

The results of this study are in line with the results of Mongan (2019) research; Septriani (2023); Ikbal (2021); Winarti (2014) also found that education has a negative influence on the human development index. According to Winarti (2014), this is because the allocation of the education budget is not all allocated to improve the quality of education, but is also allocated for other things such as employee salaries, and other education costs. According to Morgan (2019), in order for the central and regional governments to be able to optimize funds for education in order to improve the quality of human resources, the allocation of education expenditure must be on target. Education function expenditure that is included in the budget should not be made based on the percentage of the budget to the total budget allocation, but should pay attention to the use of the expenditure so that it can be implemented wisely and on target in order to improve the quality of human resources. Todaro and Smith (2011), stated that human capital is a productive investment in human beings which includes abilities, skills, knowledge and ideas. This is an important component to support economic development, especially economic development that has a spoiler benefit scheme. Where the amount of government expenditure on the education sector will determine the magnitude of development achievements.

Furthermore, based on the t-test, the results were obtained that partially health function expenditure had a positive and significant effect on the human development index at α (5%). These results show that when there is an increase in health function expenditure, the human development index also increases. This is because the increase in government expenditure on health functions has a positive impact on increasing human resource productivity. One of the efforts made by the Regency/City Government in Bengkulu Province is by allocating public expenditure for the health sector. If viewed based on data obtained from the Directorate General of Financial Balance, Ministry of Finance. The amount of health function expenditure of Regencies/Cities in Bengkulu Province has always increased from year to year, as well as the human development index, which has also increased from year to year. This is in line with Adolf Wagner's theory of government expenditure, which is known as the "law of ever-increasing activity" and then retested by Peacock and Wiseman. This theory states that government expenditure and government activities are increasing over time (Wilantari, 2012).

The variables of health function expenditure and human development index have a positive relationship with the increasing trend. This shows that the government's policy in allocating health function expenditure during the 2017-2021 period has had a significant impact on improving the quality of human resources, which can be seen from the increase in the human development index in Bengkulu Province. According to Tjptoherijianto (1989), health is one of the factors that affect the quality of human resources. Therefore, government expenditure on the health budget sector is spent to fulfill one of the basic rights to obtain health services in the form of facilities and health services which

are a prerequisite for increasing public productivity (Todaro & Smith, 2003). According to Barro (1996), health status as measured by life expectancy is the main contributor to economic growth, even its position is more important than education. According to Razmi et. Al (2012), with the improvement of health, it will increase productivity and labor supply.

In the law, it is stated that health is a human right so that the government has the responsibility to fulfill the health of every citizen. In this case, one form of government concern for improving the welfare of the people of Regencies/Cities in Bengkulu Province is by increasing the health sector budget. According to Putra (2015), humans have a role as subjects or actors as well as objects in development. This is because health is a basic need for every human being, without health humans will not be able to produce something productive for the country. A country will run well if there is health insurance for its residents.

The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Harsono et al (2024); Ratuludji et al (2024); Purnomoratih & Ramadhani (2023); Pratama & Mandai (2023); Pratama & Sumiyarti (2023); Septriani (2023); Halim et al (2022); Ndaguba and Hlotywa (2021); Sari et.al (2022); Ernita (2022); Ardiningrum et al. (2021); Maulina & Andriyani (2020); Haile & Nino-Zarazua (2018); Harjunadhi & Rahmawati (2020), Anantika & Sasana (2020); which also found that health function expenditure has a significant influence on the increase in the human development index. Likewise, the results of research conducted by Mongan (2019) found that central government expenditure in the health sector has a positive influence on the human development index. Furthermore, according to Mongan (2019) stated that the right investment in the health sector will have a positive impact on human development. The use of allocations for the construction of health buildings such as hospitals and health centers, as well as the procurement of drugs and medical equipment can improve the quality of health owned by the community. Increasing public awareness about healthy lifestyles also has a positive impact on improving public health.

Furthermore, based on the t-test, the results were obtained that partially economic function expenditure had a positive and significant effect on the human development index of districts/cities in Bengkulu Province at α (5%). These results show that when there is an increase in economic expenditure, the human development index also increases. This is because the increase in government expenditure, economic functions have a positive impact on increasing human resource productivity. This can be seen from the structure of Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget on economic functions used to finance programs in economic sectors in the region such as the agriculture, trade, and MSME sectors. This has had a positive impact on the people of Bengkulu Province, where the human development index is increasing. Although the increase is not too significant. This economic expenditure is an expenditure used to create jobs, build public facilities and infrastructure, and trigger an increase in people's economic activities. Based on data obtained from the Regional Office of the Directorate General of Treasury of Bengkulu Province (2021), Economic Expenditure data is the sum of infrastructure expenditure, food security and social protection. The average realization of economic function expenditure over the last 5 (five) years is IDR 772.1 billion. The largest realization of economic functions was in 2021 with a value of IDR 931.7 billion.

The results of this study show that economic function expenditure has a positive effect on the human development index in Regencies/Cities of Bengkulu Province. Means. When economic function expenditure increases, the human development index also increases. This positive influence means that the realization of economic function expenditure contributes to the improvement of the economy and the increase in people's income and will affect the prosperity of the community. The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Putra (2017); Ana (2017); stated that economic expenditure has a positive and significant effect on the Human Development Index. The results of this study are different from the results of Anggarista's (2022); Amar & Satria (2020) study, which found that economic function expenditure has no effect on the human development index.

Based on the t-test, the results were obtained that partially the expenditure of the social protection function had no effect on the human development index at α (5%). This means that the amount of social protection function expenditure in Bengkulu province does not have an impact on the human development index. The social protection program in the State Budget is indeed directed to overcome poverty and inequality, as well as improve the living standards of low-income people. With this social protection program, it is hoped that it will be able to improve the welfare of the community, which will ultimately have an impact on improving the ability to live a decent life and the ability of the community to meet the needs of education and health. However, social protection function expenditure has no effect on poverty, According to Septriani (2023), this is because the majority of programs carried out in social protection are poverty mitigation in the short term. So that the amount of social protection function expenditure does not have an impact on poverty in Bengkulu Province. As explained by Scott (2012), traditionally social protection has only been concentrated or focused on social protection programs in the short term. This short-term program is considered less effective because it spends a large budget, but on the other hand it does not encourage people to become more economically independent, so that the program has not been able to overcome the problem of poverty. This short-term poverty alleviation program is gradually focused on preventive as well as promotive programs for the long term. According to Guhan (1994), this is because social protection includes protection, protection and promotion components.

In addition, the lack of effect of social protection function expenditure against poverty is due to government policies that are less favorable to the underprivileged groups. Prasetyo et al. (2023), said that government expenditure in Bengkulu Province is still not on target. At a time when the realization of government programs in poverty alleviation tends to still not be on target, social assistance should really be given to people who deserve to receive the assistance (Sendouw, 2017). So, even though the government has a perfect program, it is not accompanied by strict supervision, commitment and consistency from the government, no matter how good the program is, it will not have a significant impact on the community (Septriani, 2023). In this case, social protection expenditure is not able to overcome the problem of poverty, so that welfare society (HDI) has also not been improved. The types of social assistance in the State Budget include the Family Hope Program, Basic Food Cards, the Smart Indonesia Program, the Education Assistance for Outstanding Poor Students (Bidikmisi) or the Smart Indonesia Card, and the National Health Insurance

Contribution Assistance. In addition, the Government provides additional and expanded Perlinsos programs during the pandemic, including additional benefits of the Basic Food Program, Bulog Rice Assistance, and electricity discounts aimed at maintaining the purchasing power of the poor and vulnerable groups.

The results of this study are in line with the results of a study conducted by Siregar et al (2023), showing that the social protection function expenditure variable has a positive but not significant effect on HDI. According to (National Development Planning Agency, 2020), the importance of accurate data on social assistance recipients is also a concern, because social assistance is one of the important instruments to prevent vulnerable groups and allocate government budgets. Cooperation between various parties, including local governments, is needed to collect accurate data on social assistance recipients. The results of this study are in line with the results of a study conducted by Siregar et al (2023), showing that the social protection function expenditure variable has a positive but not significant effect on HDI.

Conclusions

Based on the regression results of the panel data, a random effect model was obtained as the best model. The results of the study based on the t-test obtained the result that partially education function expenditure had a negative effect on the human development index, while health function expenditure and economic function expenditure had a positive and significant effect on the human development index, while social protection function expenditure had no effect on the human development index in districts/cities in Bengkulu Province. Meanwhile, simultaneously, education function expenditure, health function expenditure, economic function expenditure and social protection function expenditure have a positive and significant effect on the human development index in districts/cities in Bengkulu Province. The value of the coefficient terminated in this research model is 0.6631, which means that the ability of the variables education function expenditure, health function expenditure, economic function expenditure, and social protection function expenditure is able to achieve a human development index of 66.31 percent, while 33.69 percent is explained by variables outside the model. Therefore, in the next study, researchers can add other variables that theoretically affect the human development index. Furthermore, Based on this research, The regency/city government of Bengkulu Province can increase the human development index by maximizing the management of health function expenditure and the economy, as well as improving the pattern of allocating funds to education function expenditure so that it can have an impact on increasing the average length of schooling and the expectation of school length of the people of Bengkulu Province, as well as providing social protection assistance to people who are really economically vulnerable. The regency/city government of Bengkulu Province can increase the human development index by maximizing the management of health function expenditure and the economy, as well as improving the pattern of allocating funds to education function expenditure so that it can have an impact on increasing the average length of schooling and the expectation of school length of the people of Bengkulu Province, as well as providing social protection assistance to people who are really economically vulnerable.

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